

ACADEMIC STRESS AS A CORRELATE OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG UNDERGRADUATES IN NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY, AWKA

**Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie Ph.D., Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu Ph.D.,
Divine Chinemelum Ugwuele and Mirian Chioma Okpala**

*Department of Guidance and Counselling, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka,
Anambra State*

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Abstract: *This study investigated academic stress as a correlate of academic achievement among undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Three research questions guided the study, and one null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population for this study consisted of 11,039 second year undergraduates from all the 16 faculties in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The sample of the study consisted of 1,076 undergraduates drawn through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instruments used for the study was Academic Stress Scale (ASS) with a reliability coefficient alpha of 0.72. Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used for data analysis. Results obtained from the study showed that majority of the undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University have high academic stress. The results also revealed that majority of the university undergraduates have average academic achievement in Communication in English. Finally, the result showed academic stress is a high negative significant correlate of the university undergraduates' academic achievement in Communication in English. The study concluded, among others that university undergraduates' level of academic stress is a high negative significant correlate of their academic achievement. It was recommended, among others that since many of the university undergraduates are experiencing high academic stress which could be the reason for their poor academic achievement, university counsellors should design effective stress management intervention strategies to help undergraduates adequately cope with stressors in the universities.*

**Alphonsus Ekejiuba Oguzie Ph.D., Eberechukwu Francisca Chigbu Ph.D., Divine
Chinemelum Ugwuele and Mirian Chioma Okpala**

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Introduction

From inception, university education was established as a formal learning stage after secondary education that offers degree and professional training to prepare individuals for higher-level career and societal development. Hence, as a critical component of human development worldwide, university education is created to provide a platform for acquiring specialized knowledge, developing critical thinking skills, and building a strong profession network. Oftentimes, university undergraduates face immense pressure to meet the demands of their academic pursuits. In practical sense, the complex assignments and rigorous academic tasks presented to university undergraduates often pose severe challenges leading to heightened levels of stress, which can manifest as burnout, anxiety, and eventually poor academic achievements.

Conceptually, academic achievement is a symbol that indicates the level of knowledge/experience a student has acquired in a particular course of study and their ability to communicate this knowledge/experience in oral or written form (Engel, Benneth & Bishin, 2014). It is a measure of excellence in all academic exercises in class as well as extra curriculum activities. Academic achievement as

Manhood and Igbal (2015) opined is the education goal that is achieved by students, teachers or institutions over a certain period. Academic achievement has to do with students' ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate their knowledge orally or in writing form even in an examination condition. Mkpae and Obowu (2017) also asserted that academic achievement is a term usually employed to describe a students' performance in subjects taught and tested in schools. Okafor, Obi and Oguzie (2018) viewed academic achievement as the overall measured cognitive, affective and psycho-motor achievement of students with which they are judged academically fit or unfit.

In clearer terms, academic achievement depicts students' scholastic ability and attainment, which signifies the overall level of knowledge they have acquired in school, a subject or a learning situation (Oguzie, Nwokolo, Mokwelu & Ezunu, 2019). Succinctly, Ozuome, Oguzie, Mokwelu and Anyamene (2020) described academic achievement as the yardstick with which educational outcomes are measured. Furthermore, academic achievement can be described as the outcome of education that indicates the extent to which the students, teachers, curricular, counsellor or the educational institution has achieved the predetermined educational goals (Okudo &

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Obumse, 2023). For the purpose of this study, academic achievement is the product of teaching and learning that indicates the extent to which individuals in training (learners), teachers and the educational institution have achieved the predetermined educational goals and objectives.

Generally, as a multidimensional construct that includes several academic substrates, such as learning skills, attitude, interest and ability of learners, academic achievement occupies a vital position in the education system as well as in the learning process. Academic achievement appears to be complex and a fundamental principle in judging student's performance or capacity. Practically, academic achievement is very important for students, teachers, parents, government and the society in general. In the academia, students are declared geniuses or dummies based on their academic achievement. This may be probably because educational attainment is highly fundamental to the realization of the scientific, technological, socio-economic and political development of any nation as well as the total empowerment and transformation of the citizens. Moreso, academic achievement of students tends to influence their vocational career, self –esteem, motivation, and the individual's coping ability. Therefore, university undergraduates' academic achievement is of utmost importance to the

wealth of a nation and its prosperity because this level of education is so crucial to the human capital development of every nation.

In practice, the Nigeria system of education makes use of academic achievement to indicate the level of students' knowledge acquisition. This is because, academic achievement of students especially those in higher institutions is not only a pointer to the effectiveness of schools or curriculum, but a major determinant of the future of the youths in particular and the nation in general. However, in recent times, the problem of poor academic achievement of students in institutions of higher learning has become topical in most literature and has attracted the attention of stakeholders such as parents, lecturers, counsellors, school administrators, and researchers as well (Shahjahan, Ahmed, Hadrami, Islam, Hossain & Khan, 2021). A study by Okolo, Ofielu, Nebo and Obikeze (2017) found that many students in Nigerian universities perform below expectation in their academics. Similarly, Anas, Usman, Abdullahi and Jalo (2023) in their study with university students in Gombe observed that many of the students have poor academic achievement.

Moreover, another study was carried out by Offor and Offiah (2023) on academic achievement of male and female undergraduates in public universities in

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Anambra State. The results of the study showed that there was high poor academic achievement among undergraduates in public universities in Anambra State. The results also revealed that lack of suitable learning material, inability to pay school fees on time, lack of money to pay for hostel accommodation, high rate of premarital sex and cohabitation which are all caused by poverty are responsible for the poor academic achievement among university undergraduates in Anambra State. Judging from the above observations by previous researchers, it appears that the Nigerian university system is plagued by academic under-achievement. In this regard, Daniel and Abide (2023) asserted that the goal of education has not been achieved judging from the poor academic achievement of students in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Undeniably, the problem of poor academic achievement has become a worrisome phenomenon because of its tendency to affect students' overall success in life and the likelihood that under-achieving students may resort to anti-social behaviours like drug abuse, robbery, alcoholism, withdrawal from school among others, as coping mechanisms. Braide (2018) posited that the standard of education has not only fallen in Nigerian but will continue to fall if necessary measures are not taken to arrest the trend. This fallen standard of education is possibly indicated by the poor

academic achievement of students in the country. Hence, poor academic achievement among university students has become a phenomenon of interest and scholars have been working hard to untangle factors impacting on the academic achievement of university students.

Available researches have shown that several factors such as academic stress, self-esteem, peer influence, classroom climate, locus of control, emotional intelligence, lack of proper orientation programmes and learning styles may be responsible for students' academic achievement either separately or jointly (Ozuome, Oguzie, Onwukwe & Emeji, 2024). In a study carried out by Oduwaiye, Yahaya, Amadi and Tihamiyu (2017) to empirically unravel the factors influencing the academic achievement of university students in Kwara state, it was observed that academic stress is the major cause of poor academic achievement among the students. Musa (2018) also concluded that stress is a significant negative correlate of students' academic achievement. Jiboyewa and Muhammad (2015) in their study on poor academic achievement among university students in Maiduguri opined that university environment in Nigeria is largely unfavourable for high academic achievement. In particular, Asiegbu, Ezewuzie, and Emmasiegbu (2023) in their study concluded that poor academic

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achievement of students in Nnamdi Azikiwe is as a result of academic stress caused by far distance from the school to hostels, examination timetable that are not spaced out for students to have time to prepare well, high school fees, long lecture periods and poor eating habit.

Conceptually, stress is a negative emotional, cognitive, behavioural and physiological process that occurs as a person tries to adjust to or deal with stressors. According to Pratiksha and Souza (2018), stress is a response of an individual to a perceived or encountered threat or demand, which is beyond his/her ability to handle. Vinayak, Parashurama, Maresha and Sumalatha (2024) viewed stress as emotional strain resulting from academic pressures such as exams, assignments, and the pressure to succeed. Stress occurs when there is a discrepancy between environmental demands, known as stressors, and an individual's ability to fulfil those demands.

Specifically, academic stress refers to the physical or mental strain induced by various academic stressors that students encounter. Aafreen, Priya and Gayathri (2018) observed that academic stress often arises from academic pressures, personal expectations, or environmental factors that impact mental and emotional well-being. Academic stress within the university education system encompasses stressors such as heavy workloads, time

management issues, fear of failure, high expectations from lecturers and parents, peer competition, and lack of adequate resources or support. In the context of this study, academic stress is defined as a psychological and physiological response to academic challenges or demands that exceed a student's ability to cope effectively. Academic stress may adversely impact on university undergraduates' psychological well-being, leading to anxiety, burnout, and poor academic performance.

In today's world, university undergraduates experience stress from different sources, such as pressure from academic expectations, academic workloads, relationships, and social pressures. The interplay between academic stressors and their consequences highlights the critical need for strategies that mitigate their adverse effects while promoting resilience among students. A significant contributor to academic stress is the difficulty students' face in managing their time effectively. Striving to balance academics, extracurricular activities, and personal responsibilities often results in procrastination and inadequate preparation for examinations (Azila-Gbettor, Atatsi, Danku & Soglo, 2015; Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015). Moreso, poor time management not only intensifies academic stress but also compromises students' ability to meet deadlines and maintain academic

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consistency, perpetuating a cycle of underperformance and mounting pressure.

Financial difficulties further compound the stress experienced by many undergraduate students. The need to juggle part-time work alongside academic responsibilities can dilute focus and engagement, leaving students overstretched and unable to perform at their best (Allam, 2011; Brobbey, 2021). Financial strain not only hampers their ability to prioritize studies but also exacerbates feelings of inadequacy and helplessness. Motivation also plays a pivotal role in academic success, yet many students find themselves disengaged from their coursework. A lack of connection to the material often results in under-performance, causing a sense of futility that heightens stress. Previous research emphasizes the importance of creating academic environments that foster motivation and active engagement to counteract these effects (Bryne, 2016).

Furthermore, mental health challenges, such as anxiety and depression seem widespread among university students and have profound implications for their academic success. These conditions disrupt students' ability to concentrate, retain information, and meet deadlines, further intensifying the pressure they face (Bale & Epperson, 2015; Brobbey, 2021). The impact of stress can manifest in unpleasant emotional and physiological changes, often

resulting in mental and physical health issues among students. Without adequate support, mental health struggles can spiral, creating barriers to both personal well-being and academic achievement. In the face of mounting stress, many students adopt maladaptive coping mechanisms, including avoidance and substance use. These strategies, though temporarily relieving, ultimately exacerbate academic struggles by failing to address the root causes of stress (Heffer & Willoughby, 2017). Encouraging the development of healthier coping mechanisms is essential for fostering resilience and sustained academic success.

Technically, academic stress may exert a profound influence on students' performance, serving both as a motivator and a barrier. While moderate stress, or eustress, can enhance motivation and productivity, excessive distress impairs cognitive functions and diminishes academic outcomes (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015). Chronic academic stress disrupts learning processes by limiting students' ability to absorb and retain information, redirecting their focus from long-term goals to short-term relief (Marie, 2021). Academic stress also takes a toll on physical and mental health, further hindering students' ability to meet academic expectations (Reschly, Huebner, Appleton & Antaramian, 2018). In practical sense, the lack of robust support systems for handling stress

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among university students exacerbates these effects, highlighting inequities in coping resources.

Without doubt, the contemporary Nigerian university campuses contend with large class sizes, limited resources, and a high demand for access to education. Yogie, Suryadi and Soefijanto (2021) emphasized that these stressors can lead to emotional, physical, or psychological strains, potentially affecting students' ability to achieve their academic goals. More so, Sedlak (2024) opined that extreme academic stress can lead to physical and psychological impairments, further affecting students' academic and personal lives.

Without dubiety, poor academic achievement among university students has been an issue of great concern to the students, teachers, university administrators, employers of labour, and the government as well, as the strength of any nation rests greatly on the quantity and quality of its manpower. Correspondingly, research available in literature have shown that excessive academic stress has detrimental effects on students' academic performance (Ronald, 2018; Roy, Roy & Nayak, 2023). Consistent exposure to high level of stress can lead to anxiety, depression, and sleep disorders, which further exacerbate academic difficulties. Asiegbu, Ezewuzie, and Emmasiegbu (2023) in their study observed that most undergraduates

in Nnamdi Azikiwe University have high level of stress which has in-turn lead to poor academic achievement among the students. Consequent upon the apparent persistent unsatisfactory achievement of Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates in Communication in English, the present researchers deemed it necessary to replicate the study of Asiegbu and his group to further explore the relationship between academic stress and academic achievement in Communication in English among undergraduates of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the academic stress scores of Nnamdi Azikiwe University undergraduates?
2. What are the academic achievement scores of Nnamdi Azikiwe University undergraduates in communication in English?
3. What is the relationship between academic stress and academic achievement in communication in English of Nnamdi Azikiwe University undergraduates?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between academic stress and academic

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achievement in communication in English of Nnamdi Azikiwe University undergraduates.

Method

The study was carried out in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State. This study will adopt the correlation research design. The population of the study comprised all the 11,039 (4,200 male and 6,839 female) second year undergraduates from all the 16 faculties in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The sample size for the study consisted of 1,120 second year undergraduates. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used for the sampling. The instrument used for data collection was Academic Stress Scale (ASS) developed by Roy, Roy and Nayak in 2023. ASS is a self-report psychometric scale which was developed to measure academic stress of public university undergraduates. The instrument contains 29 items. The item statements in the Academic Stress Scale for this study were directed towards measuring the university undergraduates' academic stress. The instrument is on a four-point scales of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) with assigned weight of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. When administering the ASS, the respondents were requested to read the items of the instrument carefully and choose the option to describe their thoughts and feeling by ticking (4-1). All responses for the 29 items on

Academic Stress Scale were computed together to yield a total score of 116. The maximum score for each item is 4 points. So, the maximum obtainable score for this scale is 116 points, while the minimum obtainable score is 29 points. The Academic Stress Scale (ASS) for this study has proven to have good psychometric properties. Roy, Roy and Nayak in 2023 obtained an overall reliability coefficient of 0.75 Cronbach alpha using the test-retest in an interval of three weeks. The undergraduates' academic achievement scores in communication in English were obtained from their examination results in the General Studies (GS) Unit of the university. Hence, the students' scores in the communication in English course in their last semester examination was used to represent their academic achievement scores.

The researchers administered copies of the Academic Stress Scale (ASS) through direct delivery method. Data collected for this study were scored following the scoring instructions of the instrument. All the data to be collected for this study were organised in tables and analysed. Descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyse the data. Data collected for the research questions 1 and 2, were analysed using aggregate scores, while research question 3 was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). Data

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relating to the null hypothesis was analysed by comparing the already established relationship index against the critical values at 0.5 level of significance. The statistical software that was used for the analysis was the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 2023.

Table 1: Range of scores on university undergraduates’ academic stress

Range of scores	N	%	Remark
29 – 72.49	351	32.62	Low academic stress
72.50 – 116	725	67.38	High academic stress

Table 1 showed that 725(67.38%) of the undergraduates with the scores ranging from 72.50 to 116 have high academic stress, while 351(32.62%) of the undergraduates who scored between 29 to 72.49 have low academic stress.

Table 2: Range of achievement scores of undergraduates in communication in English

Range of scores	N	%	Remark
0 – 49	106	9.85	Poor achievement
50 – 69	622	57.81	Average achievement
70 – 100	348	32.34	High achievement

Table 2 indicated that 622(57.81%) of the undergraduates with the scores ranging from 50 to 69 have average achievement in communication in English, while 348(32.34%) undergraduates who scored between 70 and 100 have high achievement whereas 106(9.85%) of

Results

Research Question 1

What are the academic stress scores of Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates?

Research Question 2

What are the academic achievement scores of Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates in Communication in English?

the undergraduates have low achievement in communication in English.

Research Question 3

What is the relationship between Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates’ academic stress and their academic achievement in communication in English?

Table 3: Pearson r on university undergraduates’ academic stress and their achievement in communication in English

Source of Variation	N	Academic stress r	Achievement r	Remark
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Academic stress	1076	0.00	-0.70	High relationship	negative
Achievement	1076	-0.70	0.00		

In table 3, it was observed that there is high negative relationship of -0.70 between the university undergraduates’ academic stress and their academic achievement in communication in English.

Table 4: Significant of Pearson r on the undergraduates’ academic stress and their achievement in communication in English using probability table of r

N	cal. R	Df	Pvalue	Cal.pvalue	Remark
1076	-0.70	1075	0.05	0.00	S

S = Significant

Data in Table 4 revealed that at 0.05 level of significance and 1075df, the calculated r-0.70 has pvalue 0.00 which is less than the critical pvalue 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This signifies that there is significant relationship between Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates’ academic stress and their academic achievement in communication in English.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study showed that majority of the undergraduates (67.38%) in Nnamdi Azikiwe University have high level of academic stress. This finding indicated that many of the undergraduates are battling with stressors arising from their academic environment. This finding may be an indicator of the presence of

Null Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates’ academic stress and their academic achievement in communication in English.

many stress inducing factors in Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Furthermore, the high level of academic stress found in this study signifies that the university environment is less stressful to the undergraduates. This finding is consistent with the reports from previous researchers (Jiboyewa & Muhammad, 2015; Oduwaiye, Yahaya, Amadi & Tiamiyu, 2017; Ronald, 2018; Asiegbu, Ezewuzie & Emmasiegbu, 2023) that majority of university undergraduates have high academic stress. Aafreen, Priya and Gayathri (2018) observed that academic stress often arises from academic pressures, personal expectations, or environmental factors that impact mental and emotional well-being.

Another finding of this study showed that majority of the undergraduates (57.81%) in Nnamdi Azikiwe University have average

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academic achievement in communication in English. This result indicated that the level of academic achievement of the undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe is below expectation despite various effort made by the lecturers and university management to provide seamless, quality, interesting teaching in serene classroom environment. The above finding agrees with the reports of (Jiboyewa & Muhammad, 2015; Okolo, Ofielu, Nebo and Obikeze, 2017; Braide, 2018; Anas, Usman, Abdullahi and Jalo, 2023; Roy, Roy & Nayak, 2023; Hauwa, Shehu & Dayo, 2024) who found that many undergraduates perform below expectation, hence, the number of carryovers in semester examinations continue to increase. The finding further supported the previous finding of Asiegbu, Ezewuzie and Emmasiegbu (2023) who found that many undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University obtain poor academic achievement. The average academic achievement recorded by most undergraduates in this study is not surprising since many of the students complain about the overwhelming academic workload coupled with very limited time schedule and harsh academic environment.

Finally, the finding of the study revealed a high negative significant relationship between the Nnamdi Azikiwe university undergraduates' academic stress and their academic

achievement in communication in English. This finding indicated that the level of academic stress experienced by the university undergraduates highly influenced the grade they obtained in communication in English in their semester examination, though in the negative direction. It equally means that as the undergraduates' academic stress scores increases, their academic achievement scores in communication in English decreases (i.e. the higher the students' level of academic stress, the lower their academic achievement in communication in English), vice versa. This finding agreed with the report of previous researchers (Bedewy & Gabriel, 2015; Prabu, 2015; Borah, Chitraka and Khatiwora, 2022; Hauwa, Shehu & Dayo, 2024 ;) which concluded that school-related stress significantly correlated negatively with their academic achievement. This finding of the study also supports the findings of Asiegbu, Ezewuzie, and Emmasiegbu (2023) who reported that the relationship between students' school-related stress and their academic achievement in Use of English were significantly high in the negative direction.

The possible reason for the high significant correlation observed between the undergraduates' academic stress and their academic achievement may be because of the intense pressure faced by the students in other

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to grapple with the complexities of university education. Supporting this reason, Marie (2021) opined that chronic academic stress disrupts learning processes by limiting students' ability to absorb and retain information taught by lecturers, redirecting the students' focus from long-term goals to short-term relief, thereby reducing their academic achievement. Similarly, Sedlak (2024) opined that extreme academic stress can lead to physical and psychological impairments, further affecting students' academic and personal lives.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study summarized above, the researcher concluded that majority of undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University have high academic stress. The study also concluded that majority of undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe university have average academic achievement in Communication in English. Finally, it was concluded that the undergraduates' level of academic stress is a high negative significant correlate of their achievement in Communication in English.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Since many of the university undergraduates are experiencing high academic stress which could be the reason for their poor academic achievement, university counsellors

should design effective stress management intervention strategies to help undergraduates adequately cope with stressors in the universities.

2. University administrators in conjunction with the Nigerian Universities Commission should plan and structure the undergraduate academic curricular in such a way that it will not be so cumbersome on students to avoid unnecessary stress.

3. University lecturers should try to use fascinating teaching/instructional methods that will make teaching and learning more enjoyable and less stressful to their students.

4. The Students Union Government in conjunction with the university managements should establish recreational and social activities to make campus life easy and less stressful to university undergraduates.

5. The university undergraduates should focus on healthy lifestyles choices, effective time management and stress-reducing techniques such engaging in regular physical activities, social support, mindfulness meditation, and taken regular breaks for relaxation. They should also seek professional help their academic advisers and the university counselling services when the need arises.

6. Parents and caregivers should show adequate interest and support to their children's academic endeavour. They should also

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encourage their children in any way possible to carry out academic tasks without much stress.

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